

Some Aspects of Copper by Calcium Hydroxylapatite

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$\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ exchange in synthetic hydroxylapatite is facilitated by an increase in Cu^{2+} concentration, a decrease in pH of the medium of exchange and in the particle size of hydroxylapatite. Adsorption of Cu^{2+} and its accompanying diffusion into the interior of the crystals of hydroxylapatite explain the mechanism of exchange.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (CaHA) is the principle inorganic component of human skeletal system¹, has been the subject of extensive biological and physico-chemical studies due to its ability to undergo both cationic and anionic exchanges. The $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ replacement is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of copper into human skeletal system according to the following equation $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2 + n \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ca}_{(10-n)}\text{Cu}_n(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2 + n\text{Ca}^{2+}$.

Experimental

The synthetic CaHA was prepared by modified Collin's method² and heated to constant weight at 110°. The molar Ca/P value was found by complexometric method³ to be 1.68 (theoretical value 1.67). The period of equilibration required for the attainment of saturation of the exchange was determined through kinetic studies. The dependence of uptake of copper by CaHA on factors like pH of the medium of equilibration in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, concentration of Cu^{2+} ion in the range between 0.01 M to 0.1 M of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and a particle size between 45 μ to 250 μ and the kinetics of $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ exchange were investigated. 0.2 g of CaHA was equilibrated with a solution of 100 ml of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ A.R. (BDH) by shaking in air tight polyethylene containers mechanically changing the factors effecting the uptake under investigation each time while other factors were kept constant. The experimental assembly was kept in thermally insulated cabin to maintain at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to simulate biological conditions. At the end of desired period of equilibration the contents were filtered through IG₂ crucible. The residue was washed with doubly distilled water till it is free from adsorbed copper and the calcium and copper

content of the residue was determined by method specially worked out for this purpose⁴.

Results and Discussion

The results of uptake of copper by CaHA were represented diagrammatically Fig. 1. The uptake of Cu^{2+} by CaHA was found to (i) decrease with increase of pH of the medium of equilibration in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 (ii) increase with increase of concentration of Cu^{2+} ion and (iii) increase with decrease in the particle size of CaHA. The uptake of Cu^{2+} is found to be very rapid initially within the first 60 min (7.4 wt %) and remains almost constant (Fig. 1). The uptake varies linearly from 12.5 to 14.5 wt % as the pH decreases from 8.0 to 5.0 (Fig. 1A), it was also a linear function of increase from 3.4 to 13.1 wt % as the concentration of the medium of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution increases from 0.01 to 0.1 M (Fig. 1B). Fig. 1C shows that the uptake under a given set of experimental conditions increases from 18.6 to 22.4 wt %, as the mean radius of the particles decreases from 250 μ to 45 μ .

The fact that the exchange increases with a decrease in the particle size of CaHA (Fig. 1C) and with an increase in Cu^{2+} concentration (Fig. 1B) leads to the conclusion that the first rapid stage is surface dependent and the second stage of the exchange may be diffusion controlled and hence slow.

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